

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: RUSSIA

Guarding Freshwater Ecosystems in the Moscow Region

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Moscow - the largest megacity in Europe - is located in a place without sufficient water resources to supply all of its 17 million inhabitants with drinking water. To meet the water needs of the growing city, two hydrotechnical systems were created during the 20th century in the upper reaches of the Moskva and Volga rivers (Fig. 1). The first large reservoir on the Volga – Ivankovo - was constructed precisely to supply water to Moscow. In total, more than 10 reservoirs have been built to supply drinking water to the greater Moscow metropolitan area.

Fig. 1 Location of the Moscow Drinking Water Supply System.

The Moskva River water supply system includes 4 main reservoirs: Mozhaysk, Ruza, Istra and Ozerna. Currently, this system provides about 80% of the total annual drinking water consumption in the Moscow metropolitan area. In 1965, a laboratory for reservoir studies was established at the largest of these reservoirs- Mozhaysk – by the Faculty of Geography of Lomonosov Moscow State University. This laboratory has been conducting complex research on these reservoirs almost from the moment of their construction. In the 1970s, the laboratory actively monitored the ecosystem of the newly created Mozhaysk Reservoir, publishing the results in several monographs. In the 1980s, when more attention in the Soviet Union had turned to pollution of natural waters, the focus of limnological research of the laboratory shifted to studying the phosphorus cycle in the reservoir and the key hydrological and physical processes behind it. In the 1990s, the extent of monitoring carried out by the laboratory dropped due to the economic crisis, and during the next 20 years was limited to only studying lake physics. However, the situation has improved considerably in the last 12 years: comprehensive monthly monitoring was resumed, with

regular measurements of concentrations of nutrients and organic substances, adding chlorophyll measurement for the first time. With guidance from GLEON, an optimized monitoring program was developed, and high-frequency monitoring of temperature, oxygen and chlorophyll at the deepest point of the reservoir was started (Fig. 2). Additionally, in the last 10 years the laboratory began to publish the results of its research, making it available to researchers from other countries.

Limnological studies on reservoirs in the Moscow region are becoming more and more relevant because all reservoirs in the Moscow River basin are eutrophic with harmful algal blooms (HABs), usually cyanobacteria, occurring every few years (Fig. 3). At the same time, Russian water supply services do not monitor concentrations of either chlorophyll content or cyanotoxins in drinking water and its

Fig. 2 Buoy installed in the Mozhaysk Reservoir and saving data from loggers

sources, and the only data relevant to algal blooms received at water supply stations are information on the number of different algae divisions. That is why limnological research conducted by LMSU scientists is devoted first of all to understanding which processes control blooms in these reservoirs and to finding mechanisms of reducing the intensity of these blooms.

Reservoirs on the Moskva River have catchments with relatively low anthropogenic impact: even 50 years ago agriculture was not intensive, and in the last 30 years it has almost disappeared. At the same time, in recent decades urban development along the shores of the reservoir is continuously increasing with almost no control

Fig. 3 A harmful algal bloom (a) and fish kill (b) in the Mozhaysk Reservoir in summer with low water level.

of sewage discharge from newly built houses. Reservoirs are also popular recreational areas and attract more and more people, including non-organized tourists, who leave behind significant quantities of garbage. All this together with global warming as an additional driver, increases algal blooms in reservoirs even under low nutrient loading with river flow.

The key nutrient source here is the internal nutrient load, which results in high concentrations of inorganic nitrogen and phosphorus released from bottom sediments under anoxic conditions in summer.

Climate warming in recent decades has resulted in about a doubling of maximum concentrations of phosphorus and nitrogen in the hypolimnion during periods of summer hypoxia, which is primarily controlled by an increase in the duration of stratification. At the same time, the number of storms in summer has significantly increased in the Moscow region over the last 10-15 years, which temporarily disrupt stratification and cause a release of nutrients accumulated in hypolimnion into the surface layers.

The analysis of long-term data from the Mozhaysk Reservoir revealed that the key controlling factor behind the intensity of cyanobacterial blooms is the water level. Direct correlation between cyanobacterial biomass and chlorophyll *a* content with water level was confirmed by both observational data and model simulations. For instance, when in

2008-2009 the level of the reservoir dropped down to the minimum permissible levels due to construction work at the dam, resuspension of nutrients caused a harmful algal bloom, which lasted for one and a half months. Draining of spawning areas and dangerous algal blooms in the Mozhaysk Reservoir resulted in many fish kills over the years, and unfortunately there were no assessments of the damage to the reservoir ecosystem caused by dam repairs. The last harmful algal bloom event observed in the Mozhaysk Reservoir was in 2019, when the reservoir was not completely filled in spring due to low water inflow, and summer storm events again caused resuspension of nutrients, making them bioavailable to phytoplankton. Unfavorable hydrological conditions led to phytoplankton biomass in the reservoir exceeding 100 mg/l in August, and more than 80% of this biomass was composed of toxic cyanobacteria. Phytoplankton abundance was so high that it raised serious concerns from professionals at the Moscow water supply facility and brought them in contact with laboratory experts regarding the cause of the HABs. Meanwhile, water from Mozhaysk and other reservoirs along the Moskva River water supply system continued to be used for drinking water for lack of direct measurements of cyanotoxin levels during water treatment and the complete absence of any national Russian guidelines for cyanotoxin levels in drinking water.

Research on which nutrient elements limit cyanobacteria growth have shown that nitrogen limits algal growth to a greater extent than phosphorus. However, in modern Russian limnological studies nitrogen is often not considered as an important component of the aquatic environment in the context of eutrophication control. Presently, most Russian-language studies consider only phosphorus compounds as limiting ones, and much less importance is given to monitoring the intake of nitrogen compounds.

Regrettably, in today's Russia, there is still very little integration of limnological research with decision makers and organizations involved in the treatment of drinking water. The importance of such a synergistic approach only increases in view of more frequent occurrences of HABs, which were not observed in the Moscow region some decades ago and made worse in a warming climate. Therefore, collecting long-term data, understanding the mechanisms of outbreaks and developing strategies for controlling and reducing HAB intensity and regularity is crucial for ensuring the safety of the 17 million people in the Moscow metropolitan area even in the absence of action from policy makers. The experience of many other countries shows that sooner or later the lack of action in this direction leads to water crises in cities, and the task of Moscow limnologists today is to conduct scientific research that will help explain causes of harmful algal blooms and outline ways to avoid them.

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